

FAIR Island: Real-World Examples of Place-based Open Science

Erin Robinson, Metadata Game Changers, LLC, University of Colorado, Boulder CO, 80304, email: erin@metadatagamechangers.com

Matthew Buys, DataCite, Welfengarten 1 B, 30167 Hannover, email: mattbuys@datacite.org

John Chodacki, California Digital Library, University of California, Office of the President, 1111 Franklin Street, Oakland, CA 94607, email: John.Chodacki@ucop.edu

Kristian Garza, DataCite, Welfengarten 1 B, 30167 Hannover, email: kgarza@datacite.org

Steven Monfort, Natural Reserve System, Office of Research & Innovation, University of California System, 1111 Franklin Street, 11th Floor, Oakland, CA 94607-5200, email: steve.monfort@ucop.edu

Catherine Nancarrow, California Digital Library, University of California, Office of the President, 1111 Franklin Street, Oakland, CA 94607, email: catherine.nancarrow@ucop.edu

Maria Praetzellis, California Digital Library, University of California, Office of the President, 1111 Franklin Street, Oakland, CA 94607, email: Maria.Praetzellis@ucop.edu

Brian Riley, California Digital Library, University of California, Office of the President, 1111 Franklin Street, Oakland, CA 94607, email: brian.riley@ucop.edu

Sarala Wimalaratne, DataCite, Welfengarten 1 B, 30167 Hannover, email: sarala@datacite.org

Neil Davies, Gump South Pacific Research Station, University of California, BP 244, Moorea 98728, French Polynesia; Berkeley Institute for Data Science, University of California, 190 Doe Library, Berkeley, CA 94720, USA; E-mail: ndavies@berkeley.edu

Keywords

Place-based research, FAIR Principles, CARE Principles, research data infrastructure, data policy, data management plans

Abstract

The relationship between people, place, and data underpins some of the greatest challenges and opportunities of the 21st century. While there has been general enthusiasm for and work towards Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data for Open Science, only more recently have these data-centric principles been extended into dimensions important to people and place. Notably, the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, which affect collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, and ethics. The FAIR Island Project seeks to translate these ideals into practice leveraging the institutional infrastructure provided by scientific field stations. Starting with field stations in French Polynesia as key use cases that are exceptionally well connected to international research networks, FAIR Island builds interoperability between different components of critical research infrastructure, helping connect these to societal benefit areas. The goal is not only to increase reuse of scientific data and the awareness of work happening at the field stations, but more generally to accelerate place-based research for sustainable development. FAIR Island works reflexively, aiming to scale horizontally through networks of field stations and to serve as a model for other sites of intensive long-term scientific study.

Background

Relationships between human communities and their natural and built environments are increasingly mediated through digital data. These data feed models and algorithms that impact decision-making in a range of contexts and at nested scales of governance, from the stewardship of smart cities and Indigenous lands to international agreements over global commons such as the High Seas, Antarctica, or the Earth's atmosphere. Digital representations of these complex systems (digital twins or avatars) are emerging as technology platforms that harness the predictive power of scientific understanding (e.g., the consequences of climate change), while raising vital ethical, legal, and social issues, including who should control these capabilities and how.

Many aspirations for more effective data sharing in science are situated at a high level, such as the Beijing Declaration on Research Data [1] and principles such as FAIR and CARE [2,3]. Real-world implementations are now needed to demonstrate appreciable scientific and societal benefits. Transdisciplinary predictive modeling of complex social-ecological systems, which is vital to sustainability science, relies on capacity to integrate diverse data types [4]. The FAIR Island project builds on such efforts, promoting best practices in place-based research data management. The project leverages field stations and marine laboratories in (a) French Polynesia, including the University of California (UC) Gump South Pacific Research Station on Moorea, and the Tetiaroa Ecostation, a recently established research station on the atoll of Tetiaroa (Fig 1), and (b) California, through the UC Natural Reserve System

(UCNRS), which operates 41 stations across the state. FAIR Island draws on significant data expertise provided by the Berkeley Institute for Data Science, the California Digital Library (CDL), DataCite, and Metadata Game Changers LLC.

Figure 1. Map of first two field station site locations

FAIR Island Approach

Launched in 2019 with seed funding from the University of California, FAIR Island received additional support from the National Science Foundation (NSF) in August 2021. The project focuses initially on two working field stations - one new and one well-established - that are linked to a range of international research networks in marine and terrestrial environments. Informed by experience at the Gump Station (established 1985), the new international research station (Tetiaroa Ecostation) on the private island of Tetiaroa offers an opportunity to build optimal data infrastructure and practices from the ground up, and to demonstrate the benefits for all stakeholders. Drawing on real use cases, FAIR Island contributes to the advancement and adoption of Open Science at the field stations by building interoperability between existing tools and infrastructure, including: Data Management Plans (DMPs), research practice, persistent identifiers (PIDs), data policy, and publications (Figure 2). In addition to a scientific and data-centric focus, the project also incorporates best practices with regard to ethical, legal, and social issues, such as application of the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance [3]. Our hypothesis is that improving research data infrastructure and practice across these scientific, ethical, legal and social dimensions at field stations will accelerate place-based research to solve global challenges (e.g., Sustainable Development Goals) and benefit local communities. Once the FAIR Island infrastructure is established at

the initial two stations, the common elements will be shared with other field stations in the Pacific Islands [5], California, and beyond.

Figure 2: FAIR Island Project diagram

Develop and Test Place-based Research Data Policies

At the time of writing, the Project has collected existing data policy resources, developed a draft Data Policy for the Tetiaroa Ecostation, and solicited feedback from the community, including participating in the FAIRsFAIR data policy evaluation [6]. Building from the draft Tetiaroa Data Policy, we created and published a Generic Place-Based Data Policy [7] as a template to be shared, refined, and implemented across various field stations and marine labs. By using Github for version control, the development process for this policy is fully transparent, enabling others to easily adopt and adapt it for their use.

Adapting User-Driven Systems Integrations for Networked DMPs

For more than 10 years, DMPs have been included in the proposal phase of the research lifecycle. FAIR Island now extends the use of the DMPs into the implementation phase of research by leveraging the DMPTool to establish a detailed research DMP for work at a field station and mint a DOI for that DMP. As research outputs, such as data, software, and publications, occur, they are linked to the networked DMP through persistent identifies (PIDs), creating a hub of activity about a particular research project.

Integration with other systems is a core requirement and scalable benefit of FAIR Island. These PID connections facilitate further development of the DataCite Commons interface and extend connections made possible via the networked DMP. Users can track relationships between DMPs, investigators, outputs, organizations, research methods, and protocols as well as display citations throughout the research lifecycle. A second integration with the UC Natural Reserve System (UCNRS) optimizes the UCNRS reservations management tool (RAMS¹), which is used at many field stations and provides the initial project metadata needed

¹ <https://rams.ucnrs.org/applications>

to create a DMP. This integration reduces the burden on the researcher who need not enter information twice.

As an initial integration experiment, FAIR Island selected the Moorea Biocode Project [8], which ended about 10 years ago. We created a DMP using the DMPTool with content from the original application submitted to UCNRS RAMS (see <https://dmphub.cdlib.org/dmps/doi:10.48321/D1F88S>). To find research outputs, the literature was searched for the term 'Moorea Biocode'. Identified publications and datasets were then linked through related works in the DMP. With these links established, the DataCite DMP ID Jupyter Notebook (see <https://support.datacite.org/docs/dmp-ids-in-the-pid-graph>) was used to draw three graphs (Figure 3) that simulate the way that the Persistent Identifier Graph (PID Graph) can visualize relationships across the research lifecycle.

Figure 3: Moorea Biocode PIDGraph Evolution (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6347677>)

(a) With 'discoverable' people, organizations, and funders before any works were added (other organizations, funders, and individuals could have been involved)

(b) after discoverable journal articles were added

(c) after discoverable datasets were added.

Moving forward, each research project at participating field stations will have a published DMP. Utilizing this collection of DMPs with connected outputs, we will develop a field station dashboard showing field data collection to publication, documenting all research data and

research outcomes derived from those data. These linkages will provide insight into not only direct connections, but also connections several steps removed. The understanding that the dashboard will provide an easier way for field station staff to communicate the value of the work happening at these sites to various stakeholders, including funders and local resource managers. It will also facilitate reuse of data and other research outputs to conduct new science.

Conclusions

The FAIR Island Project is iteratively adjusting to the realities on the ground as it works with real use cases at participating field stations. Each new implementation will allow us to further refine the research infrastructure. The outcomes of this Project will provide insights on optimal research data management practices and how to support place-based research more effectively. The impacts of the Project are likely to be far reaching beyond field stations – to smart cities and other place-based research sites. For more on the Project and to get involved, see the website <https://fairisland.org/>.

List of Abbreviations

CARE: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics; CDL: California Digital Library; CODATA: Committee on Data for Science and Technology; DMP: Data Management Plan; DOI: Digital Object Identifier; FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable; IDEA: Island Digital Ecosystem Avatars; NSF: National Science Foundation; PID: Persistent Identifier; RAMS: Reservation Application Management System; UCNRS: University of California Natural Reserve System;

Data Availability

Not applicable.

Funding

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under “EAGER: The FAIR Island Project for Place-based Open Science” (NSF 2132549) and “RCN: Sampling Nature: A Network to Enhance the Natural History Value Chain for Sustainability Science” (NSF 2129268). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

Declarations

Not applicable.

Consent for Publication

Not applicable.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' Contributions

Much of the text is derived from the collaborative "FAIR Island" proposal that was submitted to the National Science Foundation in Spring 2021. E.R. put together the initial draft of the present manuscript with N.D. and all authors contributed to subsequent drafts, with N.D. adding Fig. 1 and E.R. adding Fig. 2, and Fig. 3. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to the initial research teams at the UC Gump South Pacific Research Station and the Tetiaroa Ecostation with whom we have worked.

References

1. CODATA, Committee on Data of the International Science Council, CODATA International Data Policy Committee, CODATA and CODATA China High-level International Meeting on Open Research Data Policy and Practice, Hodson S, Mons B, Uhler P, et al.. The Beijing Declaration on Research Data.
2. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, et al.. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data*. 2016; doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.
3. Carroll SR, Garba I, Figueroa-Rodríguez OL, Holbrook J, Lovett R, Materechera S, et al.. The CARE principles for indigenous data governance. *Data Sci J*. Ubiquity Press, Ltd.; 2020; doi: 10.5334/dsj-2020-043.
4. Davies N, IDEA Consortium, Field D, Gavaghan D, Holbrook SJ, Planes S, et al.. Simulating social-ecological systems: the Island Digital Ecosystem Avatars (IDEA) consortium. GigaScience.
5. Lemus J, Davies N, Claudet J, Leguen A, Mawyer A, Murphy F, et al.. The 4-Site Pacific Transect Collaborative (4-Site). *Mar Technol Soc J*. 2021; doi: 10.4031/MTSJ.55.3.47.
6. O'Connor R, Garbuglia F. FAIRsFAIR review of Tetiaroa Research Data Policy. Zenodo; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6513733>
7. Davies N, Chodacki J, Praetzellis M, Nancarrow C, Robinson E. Generic Place-Based Research Data Policy. Zenodo;
8. Check E. Treasure island: pinning down a model ecosystem. *Nature*. 2006; doi: 10.1038/439378a.